

Activity Coefficients in the Adsorbed Phase

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Activity coefficients of benzene and acetic acid at 20° on the surface of tin oxide gel have been calculated making use of Everett's model of adsorption. The values vary from 1.031 to 0.8710 for acetic acid and from 0.9729 to 0.0003 for benzene upto 0.7 mole fraction of acetic acid after which phase separation starts, making calculations impossible. The values reveal strong intermolecular forces of attraction in the adsorbed phase.

SURFACE activity coefficients in a solid-liquid interface denote the escaping tendencies of the components of a liquid mixture from the surface of a solid just as activity coefficients in a liquid-vapour interface represent the escaping tendencies of the components to go into the vapour phase. The values in these two interfaces are likely to be different because surface forces besides the molecular forces play their role in the solid-liquid interface. Blackburn et al¹ investigated the surface activity coefficients of components of a number of binary liquid mixtures on the surface of carbons and graphite. They used Elton's convention² that surface activity and hence its surface activity coefficient is 1 when its mole fraction is 1 although this convention is open to criticism in the case of partly miscible liquid mixtures. They further assumed that the activity of a component in the solid and the liquid phase is the same at equilibrium. Lu and Lama³ calculated the surface activity coefficients of benzene and cyclohexane in adsorption from this liquid mixture on silica gel. They found

that activity coefficients were more than unity for both the components over the whole concentration range. It was thought of interest to take acetic acid-benzene mixture for such investigation as this mixture presents a highly non-ideal system in the liquid phase. The absorbent was tin oxide gel with the surface area of 160 m²/g whose method of preparation has been reported earlier^{4,5}. One gram of the solid was treated with 10 ml of the mixture of varying concentrations and was shaken occasionally for 24 hrs. The solutions were analysed refractometrically, the blank solutions also having been treated similarly. The temperature of adsorption was 20°. Mole fractions in the adsorbed phase were estimated by using Everett's equations⁶

$$\frac{x_1 x_2}{n_o \Delta x_2 / m} = \frac{m}{n^\sigma} \left(x_2 + \frac{1}{k-1} \right) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$\text{and } n_o \Delta x_2 / m = n_2^\sigma (x_2^\sigma - x_2) / m \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where x_1 and x_2 stand for the mole fractions of

TABLE
CALCULATION OF SURFACE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF BENZENE(1) AND ACETIC ACID(2)
IN THE ADSORBED PHASE ON TIN OXIDE GEL

	Mole fraction of acetic acid x_2 in the liquid					
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.7
x_1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.4	0.3
$x_2 r_2$	0.045	0.075	0.110	0.140	0.2	0.235
$x_1 r_1$	0.955	0.925	0.890	0.860	0.8	0.765
x_2^σ	0.486	0.7	0.786	0.890	0.843	0.886
x_1^σ	0.514	0.3	0.214	0.170	0.157	0.114
$\log \frac{x_2^\sigma x_2 r_2}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1}$	-1.3024	-1.4590	-1.4730	-1.4771	-1.3820	-1.4031
$x_1^\sigma \log \frac{x_2^\sigma x_2 r_2}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1}$	- .6694	- .4376	- .3152	- .2510	- .2091	- .1599
$\int_0^{x_2^\sigma} \log \frac{x_2^\sigma x_2 r_2}{x_2^\sigma x_1 r_1} dx_1^\sigma$	- .683	- .373	- .253	- .178	- .163	- .100
r_2^σ	1.0310	0.8618	0.8666	0.8453	0.8995	0.8710
r_1^σ	0.9729	0.4452	0.1408	0.0151	0.0462	0.0003

benzene and acetic acid respectively in the liquid phase. Δx_2 is the change in the mole fraction of acetic acid when m gram of the solid is equilibrated with n_0 moles of the liquid mixture. n^σ and x_2^σ represent the total number of moles of the components and the mole fraction of component 2 in the adsorbed phase. k is the distribution constant. Surface activity coefficients were then determined by using Everett Equation⁷.

$$\ln r_2^\sigma = x_1^\sigma \ln \left(\frac{x_1^\sigma x_2^\sigma r_1^\sigma}{x_2^\sigma x_1^\sigma r_1^\sigma} \right) - \int_0^{x_1^\sigma} \ln \left(\frac{x_1^\sigma x_2^\sigma r_2^\sigma}{x_2^\sigma x_1^\sigma r_1^\sigma} \right) dx_1^\sigma$$

For the calculation of surface activity coefficients, graphical integration which gives accurate values has been carried out. The activity coefficients in the liquid phase, r_1 and r_2 were calculated from the vapour-pressure data reported in the literature⁸. Since refractometry gives values correct up to three places of decimal, the error involved in the calculation of number of moles, mole fractions and activity coefficients in the adsorbed phase is negligible. The activity coefficient of acetic acid in the adsorbed phase varies from 1.031 to 0.8710 and that of benzene from 0.9729 to 0.0003. Calculations could

be made up to 0.7 mole fraction of acetic acid as after that phase separation starts making calculations impossible. Thus the system presents a highly non-ideal picture in the adsorbed phase. It seems reasonable to say that there are strong intermolecular forces in the adsorbed phase which decrease the tendencies of the components to escape into the liquid phase.

References

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